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Measuring urban security perception in transport from social media data to inform transport network models

A case study for Milan in 2019 and New York City in 2021

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Measuring urban security perception in transport from social media data to inform transport network models

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Urban security perception is a critical, yet understudied factor of the adequacy dimension of transport poverty. This study investigates the potential of geo-social media data to assess perceived security in urban transport networks across European cities. Using over one million geo-referenced X microblogging posts from Milan (2019) and 12 million from New York City (2021), we applied a multi-stage Natural Language Processing (NLP) pipeline, including emotion and sentiment analysis and a few-shot semantic classifier, to detect posts expressing fear and insecurity, particularly related to women’s urban mobility. These indicators were spatially aggregated and compared against reference datasets on security perception and reported crimes.

Results reveal distinct spatial patterns: Milan exhibited centralised posting with sparse, artefact-prone peripheral signals, while New York City showed more dispersed clusters in areas like the Bronx, Brooklyn, and Queens. However, correlations with ground-truth security data were consistently weak (Pearson’s $r < 0.07$), limiting social media’s reliability as a proxy for city-wide perceptions.

Supplementary analysis of geo-referenced Google Maps reviews in Milan identified higher relevance of perceived security concerns in specific place types, such as parks and public transport locations, but revealed low overall confidence scores using the social media-based models. While geo-social media offer scalable, low-cost insights, limitations in spatial granularity, platform-dependent posting behavior, and demographic bias underscore the need for refined methodologies and multimodal data integration in future research.

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Keywords

Security perception; Transport poverty; Geo-social media; Natural Language Processing (NLP); Geospatial analysis

1. Introduction

Perceived security plays a crucial role in shaping urban mobility behaviour and transport accessibility. Fear of crime or security concerns can significantly influence how individuals, particularly vulnerable groups, navigate cities (Pain, 2001). This affects travel choices, route selection, and overall quality of life (Levy, 2013). Within the broader context of transport poverty, the subjective feeling of insecurity emerges as a notable barrier to equitable access. This issue has gained increased relevance considering the European Union's strategic goals to ensure social inclusion and climate neutrality, which call for multidimensional approaches to transport planning that integrate not only physical accessibility but also experiential and perceptual factors.

Data on place-based perceived security has been traditionally collected through surveys and specialised mobile applications (Dubey et al., 2025). While valuable, these methods are typically local in focus, facing scalability limitations. The growing availability of geo-referenced user-generated social media content, particularly from mainstream global platforms like X and Google Maps, presents a promising, scalable alternative (Crooks et al., 2015). These platforms capture real-time public discourse and offer the potential to extract insights into emotional responses and perceptions at high spatial resolutions.

This study explores whether geo-social media can serve as a reliable proxy for perceived transport security. By applying advanced natural language processing and spatial analysis techniques to large-scale datasets from Milan and New York City, this study explores the strengths and limitations of this approach in informing transport equity modelling and supporting evidence-based policy development in global contexts.

1.1 Background

Geo-social media for urban perception security and analysis

Crowdsourced data sources such as geo-referenced social media posts have become established tools for supporting urban analysis, particularly in understanding aspects of human perception and security in cities (ibid.). Prior research includes both quantitative and qualitative approaches. Quantitatively, the massive amounts of geo- and time-referenced social media data available can help both in understanding and modeling urban patterns of human behaviour (Lin & Geertman, 2019).

A growing number of studies apply sentiment and emotion analysis in spatiotemporal contexts to assess how people perceive urban environments in relation to security and well-being. For instance, Kovacs-Györi et al. (2018) investigated the spatiotemporal park visiting behaviour of more than 4,000 Twitter (now X) users for approximately 1,700 parks in London, United Kingdom (UK), applying sentiment and emotion extraction to inform urban planning. Resch et al. (2016) proposed a generalised graph-based approach for emotion classification from geo-referenced social media posts in different locations within a city. Petutschnig et al. (2019) investigated public sentiment towards the renovation plan of the L train metro line in New York City using a combination keyword filtering, sentiment analysis and hotspot analysis of geo-referenced tweets. They found that tweets conveying negative sentiment clustered in lower Manhattan whereas positive or neutral hot spots were distributed across the city more evenly. Feliciano (2020) analysed geo-referenced posts in San Francisco regarding their alignment between crime-related sentiment (fear) and actual crime incidents. The findings revealed correlations in northeastern San Francisco, with peaks on Fridays at 18:00.

Other studies explore urban human perception more broadly through semantic and exploratory analyses of social media content. Guerrero et al. (2016) analysed Instagram images in Copenhagen to map cultural ecosystem services such as park usage. Yang et al. (2016) compared geo-referenced posts from Twitter (X) and Instagram across four European cities (Amsterdam, London, Paris, Rome). They found that user diversity like the ratio of tourists and residents significantly impacts data interpretation. Furthermore, contextual demographic factors such as user age influence urban activity reflections. Roberts et al. (2017) assessed the variance of physical activity engagement for urban green space between summer and winter. Bao et al. (2017) investigated whether Twitter (X) location check-in data could support the spatial

analysis of crashes in urban areas. Naaman et al. (2021) examined within-day and across-day variability of diurnal keyword patterns across different urban areas. They found that only a handful of cities provided the magnitude of content to support such analyses for more than a few keywords. Milusheva et al. (2021) used geoparsing to extract geolocated crash reports from Twitter (X) for the years 2012 to 2020 and clustered them into unique crashes. Huang et al. (2022) examined changes in Twitter (X) topics regarding the impression associated with the parks in New York City (NYC) from 2019 to 2021. Honzák et al. (2024) introduced a method for the contextual enrichment of crowds detected from mobile phone data by associating them with topics and sentiments derived from geo-referenced Twitter (X) posts. Notably, geo-social media is frequently used as an auxiliary data source, often in combination with traffic information, socio-demographic data, or mobile phone mobility data to enhance contextual understanding (Bao et al., 2017; Honzák et al., 2024).

The methodologies employed across these studies reflect a common analytical toolbox for geo-social media-based urban research. Spatiotemporal analysis techniques include spatial statistics like Getis-Ord G_i^* for hotspot analysis or temporal aggregation (Tang & Painho, 2023). To derive meaning from user-generated content, many studies apply Natural Language Processing (NLP), including polarity-based sentiment analysis and more fine-grained emotion detection to gauge public sentiment (De Oliveira & Painho, 2021). Text classification (Häberle et al., 2019) or unsupervised topic modelling (Tang & Painho, 2023) are also widely used to extract semantic patterns that reflect urban human behaviour and perceptions. While most analyses focus on textual data, the use of social media images remains comparatively limited in urban security research. Visual content is more commonly used in landscape and environmental studies (Yang & Liu, 2022). Textual geo-social media analysis for urban security detection often focuses on security event detection during times of social or political unrest (Chen et al., 2025; Han et al., 2019). The STEP UP research, based on which the current study validates security perception data in Milan, applies textual analysis to crowdsourced data from the security reporting app, *Wher*, to reveal themes in security-related perceptions from geo-referenced comments submitted to the platform (Abdelfattah et al., 2024). Alternatively, Zhang and Feik (2016) rely on text processing methods to analyse Twitter data collected for the Region of Waterloo in Ontario (Canada) with the goal of mapping citizens' concerns, including security, regarding the development of a new transit line.

1.2 Policy Context

The European Union (EU) is committed to evaluating equity of transport systems through models that assess transport accessibility to essential services and opportunities by specific modes of transport and at a detailed spatial resolution. Transport poverty is a relevant issue to be assessed by these models. This complex and multidimensional problem is characterised by lack of sufficient access experienced by individuals trying to navigate transport networks, due to availability, affordability, accessibility, or adequacy issues (European Commission, 2024). Such challenges, along with the risk of social exclusion linked to transport poverty, have gained significant attention within the EU's broader strategy to promote social inclusion and climate neutrality.

Therefore, the European Commission has acknowledged the necessity of developing indicators to identify and address areas where individuals may experience transport poverty, as outlined in its Recommendation on transport poverty (European Commission, 2025a). Emphasising the urgency of this issue, the forthcoming EU Anti-Poverty Strategy and the Social Climate Fund call for comprehensive and multidimensional approaches to improve transport equity and social inclusion at urban, regional, national and European levels (European Commission, 2025b).

Security perception of public transport and road networks is a relevant factor falling within the "adequacy of transport" dimension of transport poverty. This is one of the silent factors influencing the daily mobility choices of urban users. Negative perceptions of security in transport infrastructure or services can lead to altered travel behaviours or the complete avoidance of certain routes or streets perceived as dangerous. This disproportionately affects vulnerable groups such as women, gender minorities, children, and individuals with varying socio-economic backgrounds (Farina et al., 2022; European Investment Bank, 2024).

Traditionally, data on security perception has been collected at local or city levels through surveys or specialised applications. However, these methods face challenges such as high costs, dependency on specific contexts, and temporal biases, which make it difficult to scale up or generalise results and use them effectively to support policy implementation and monitoring activities (Kurshitashvili et al., 2022). The proliferation of social media offers a novel, cost-effective alternative for gathering sentiment and emotion data across diverse populations. This approach enables the analysis of broad public sentiments while mitigating some biases inherent in traditional survey methods. Nonetheless, the use of social media data presents challenges, including potential biases arising from digital divides and use of social media platforms, and the nature of self-reported experiences (Hook, 2024).

The integration of geo-social media data into transport models offers a potentially novel approach to understanding public perceptions of transport security. By analysing sentiment and emotion data from social media platforms, policymakers can gain insights into perceived security of the transport networks across different demographic groups. The inclusion of such information in the development of spatial accessibility indicators could then support policy decisions at various administrative levels. However, it is crucial to address privacy concerns and ensure that these data are integrated into transport models without being explicitly represented, to avoid negatively characterising transport services or road infrastructure based solely on perceived security. The European Commission's emphasis on transport poverty indicators aligns with these efforts, highlighting the relevance of integrating geo-referenced crowdsourced data from social media into transport planning to ensure a fair transition towards climate neutrality.

1.3 Research Goals

This study aims to advance the development of transport poverty indicators that address the complex accessibility challenges across Europe. By employing high-resolution spatial data and innovative methodologies, the research seeks to offer actionable insights for policy decisions, particularly in relation to the perception of security within transport networks—a factor that significantly influences mobility choices and can exacerbate transport poverty.

The study explores the potential of geo-social media as a novel data source to assess public sentiment and perceptions of transport security, offering a scalable and cost-effective alternative to traditional survey methods. By employing advanced spatiotemporal analysis techniques and natural language processing, we aim to develop indicators that accurately identify spatial and temporal patterns in public security perception across various urban environments.

In particular, the research focuses on the implications of security perception for transport accessibility and poverty, with an emphasis on vulnerable populations. Through this approach, we aim to provide policymakers with insights to enhance transport systems for the people they should serve, ensuring they are equitable and responsive to the needs of all citizens. Ultimately, this study seeks to contribute to the broader understanding and mapping of transport security in urban environments and support the development of more inclusive and efficient transport policies throughout Europe, leveraging the potential of emerging data sources like geo-social media to complement traditional approaches.

In essence, the present study provides a cross-validated empirical reference against which sentiment classification methods applied to geosocial media can be evaluated, by comparing their outputs with ground-truth data, namely self-reported security perceptions of users in Milan and recorded crime incident locations in New York City.

2. Enabling Data

The data collection process consisted in the acquisition and the preparation of datasets from three different sources, namely (i) geo-social media data, (ii) security perception data; and (iii) geo-referenced user review data.

2.1 Geo-social Media Data

The geo-social media data sources selected as case study for this article consisted in two different datasets of posts retrieved from X (formerly Twitter). Since comparable baseline data for women's security perception was available for

the city of Milan in 2019 (Messa et al., 2025) and NYC in 2021 (Gorrini et al., 2021), data for the same period was collected from the X social media platform. The data collection was performed through the former Twitter v1.1 search and filtered streaming Application Programming Interface (API) endpoints, then the posts were filtered with a geo-location within one of the two cities and a temporal filter covering the respective years. *Table 1* provides an overview of the search criteria and the retrieved posts.

Table 1 - Overview of the filtering criteria and obtained X social media posts for the two cities of interest.

City	Bounding box	Temporal filter	Retrieved posts
Milan	POLYGON ((9.039 45.385, 9.279 45.385, 9.279 45.539, 9.039 45.539, 9.039 45.385))	2019-01-01 to 2019-12-31	980,450
New York City	POLYGON ((-74.256 40.918, -73.689 40.918, -73.689 40.496, -74.256 40.496, -74.256 40.918))	2021-01-01 to 2021-12-31	12,019,978

The retrieved data includes the post timestamp, geo-location information in the form of either a point coordinate or a bounding box, the text content, and metadata such as message and author identifiers. Bounding boxes are typically place-based and correspond to broader geographic entities, including city-level areas like Milan or landmarks such as Central Park (Khalid, 2019). The bounding boxes included in the acquired datasets are not consistent in size, as they include very large areas, such as the whole city (in cases where users geo-tag themselves in the city and not to a specific place), and smaller areas, such as specific points of interest. To avoid a misrepresentation of the spatial distribution of the posts, just the bounding boxes with *area = 0 sqm* are included in the cleaned dataset, as these exclude the city-wide or the district-wide geotags. The remaining bounding boxes are simplified to the centroid. After this process, duplicates and empty strings were removed from the data, and the posts located outside of the city boundaries of Milan and NYC were excluded.

The downstream analysis of the obtained social media posts involved several variations of text analysis, specifically sentiment and emotion detection and semantic classification. As a pre-processing step, each text was normalised by replacing usernames and links with standardised tokens (“@user” and “http”) to minimise the influence on model predictions and avoid overfitting on specific users or links during model training.

2.2 Security Perception Data

The women’s security perception data mentioned in the previous section are the results of previous works of some of the authors. In particular, the dataset for Milan is one of the outputs of the STEP UP – Walkability for Women in Milan project, which focused on the evaluation of gendered walkability due to lower security perceptions at night in the city of Milan. During the project, a synthetic “Safety Score” was estimated by calibrating a Geographically Weighted Regression model with crowdsourced perceived security street ratings. The underlying data and the process leading to the Safety Score are described respectively in Abdelfattah et al. (2024) and in Messa et al. (2025).

Conversely, the dataset describing New York City is one of the enabling data used to develop the Walkability for Women Index (Gorrini et al., 2021). The security condition is not represented here through subjective security perceptions, as in the case of Milan, but as sexual crimes reported to the New York City Police Department. Crimes and violations included in this dataset are harassment, obscenity performance, rape, sexual crimes and abuses (considering offenses occurring at intersections).

Both datasets need to be considered as inherently limited and biased, especially as descriptors for a nuanced phenomenon such as the level of perceived security. Without the objective of providing a comprehensive list, known biases for the Milan and NYC datasets are respectively: the narrow demographic distribution of the contributors of the crowdsourced security scores, for Milan; and the imbalanced opportunity and willingness to report crimes to the Police

Department of different populations, for NYC, coupled with the known limitations of reported crimes as proxies for security perception.

2.3 Geo-referenced user review data

Google Places data is explored as an alternative to the X microblogging data, with the goal of comparing the two sources in terms of content relevance and the ability to extract structured information. Specifically, reviews of heterogeneous places in the city of Milan are extracted from the Google Places data collected through the Google Maps platform, as a source of information revealing users’ subjective experiences of urban spaces. This is done with the aim to extract security-relevant information that can supplement our understanding of place-based security perceptions and offer a novel source for gathering georeferenced security perceptions in cities.

The dataset originates from a previous download of Google Places conducted in July 2024, as part of the study “*The Right to the Night City: Exploring the Temporal Variability of the 15-Minute City in Milan and Its Implications for Nocturnal Communities*” (Abdelfattah et al., 2025). Using the Nearby Search API, a total of 135,405 unique places within the boundaries of the municipality of Milan were retrieved. This API provides basic metadata for each place, including the place_id, name, coordinates, and type.

Given the spatial-context agnostic nature of places included in the Google Places database, the analysis was tailored to focus exclusively on reviews of places which generate activity in the public sphere, specifically focusing on public transport-related place types to align with the research scope of security perceptions in transport-related environments. To tailor the dataset to the research focus on open public spaces and transport environments, a filtering process was applied based on the “Google Place Types” classification. To enhance potential for detecting security-related perceptions in place reviews, only places associated with public use or nighttime activities were retained in the exploratory dataset (see Table 2), resulting in a refined dataset of 10,296 places.

Table 2 – Overview of Google Places types included in the dataset.

Google Places Types			
airport	cemetery	night_club	train_station
amusement_park	city_hall	park	transit_station
art_gallery	gas_station	parking	university
atm	hospital	subway_station	
bus_station	library	taxi_stand	
campground	light_rail_station	tourist_attraction	

Given the constraints of the Google Places Details API, which allows a maximum of 1,000 free requests, a random sample of approximately 10% of the filtered dataset was selected, yielding a final working sample of 1,009 places. The selection maintained a representative distribution of place types, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Overview of Google Places types included in the dataset.

Review data for these 1,009 places was then collected in July 2025 using the Place Details API, which provides more detailed information for each place, including up to five user reviews. This cap on review availability, limited to a maximum of five per place, is a notable constraint of the Place Details API and poses a clear limitation for comprehensive review analysis. After a cleaning and preprocessing phase, a total of 2,037 valid reviews were obtained. These reviews were written in either Italian or English and contained non-empty text. This final set of reviews was used for the subsequent analysis.

3. Methodology

3.1 Sentiment and emotion analysis

The process to extract public affective responses from X social media posts was based on a combination of emotion and sentiment analysis, leveraging state-of-the-art multilingual transformer models. This dual approach was chosen after observing that one classification model alone did not yield sufficiently reliable results.

First, the multilingual XLM-EMO-T model was implemented (Bianchi et al., 2022) for multi-label emotion detection across the two data sets. The model supports 19 languages and identifies the presence of four emotion classes: joy, anger, fear, and sadness. For each class, the model outputs a probability score, and an emotion is considered present if its probability exceeds a threshold of 0.5. If no emotion class surpasses this threshold, the post is marked as containing no emotion. The original paper reports an average macro F1-score of 0.85 across all supported languages. However, our manual review of the classification results revealed frequent misclassifications. It was, therefore, combined with an additional polarity-based classifier.

The polarity-based classifier should complement emotion detection and capture the overall sentiment polarity of each post. The selected model was the Twitter-RoBERTa-base-sentiment (Loureiro et al., 2022) for the NYC dataset, which is primarily English-language, and the multilingual Twitter-XLM-RoBERTa-base-sentiment (Barbieri et al., 2022) for the Milan dataset, which contains a mix of Italian and other languages. Both models were pre-trained on Twitter (X) data and classify posts into three categories: negative, neutral, and positive. Finally, a combination of emotion and sentiment labels, particularly the presence of fear and negative sentiment, were selected to identify posts expressing insecurity, discomfort, or perceived danger.

3.2 Few-shot semantic analysis

In addition to sentiment and emotion analysis, a semantic classification model was trained, with the objective of identifying posts specifically related to women’s perceived urban security. In this case, a Few-Shot Learning (FSL) approach was adopted, and was implemented by using manually annotated examples. A total of 141 posts, sampled from both the Milan and NYC datasets, were labelled by domain experts in transport research. Of these, 71 posts were labelled as relevant, meaning they explicitly referred to women’s security concerns. These typically involved negative experiences such as fear, harassment, or danger in urban mobility environments. The remaining 70 posts were labelled as not relevant. The labelling process was planned to ensure the inclusion of both clear-cut cases and more ambiguous examples. These included posts describing general fear or danger that were not specifically tied to women’s security perceptions in relation to perceived risks to personal safety. An example illustrating this distinction is provided in Table 3.

Table 3 - Labelled examples from both datasets (Milan 2019 and NYC 2021).

Example	Label
<p>livello di terrore di tornare da sola a casa quando c’è buio: mi sono fatta la coda bassa perché avevo paura con i codini di attirare troppo l’attenzione http</p> <p>(Translation from Italian: terror level of going home alone when it's dark: I pulled my ponytail low because I was afraid that I would attract too much attention with pigtails http)</p>	Relevant
<p>I was just walking down the street and got catcalled twice within about 5 feet...which has happened before...and I can only imagine it never happening again.</p>	Relevant
<p>Quella paura maledetta che mi prende ogni volta che comincio a uscire con una persona.</p> <p>(Translation from Italian: That damn fear that gets me every time I start dating.)</p>	Not relevant
<p>Exactly. @user is a very dangerous human being</p>	Not relevant

This labelled dataset was split into training (80%), test (20%), and validation (10%) sets, resulting in 89, 29, and 23 examples, respectively. To train the classifier, a Sentence Transformer Fine-tuning (SetFit) (Tunstall et al., 2022) was implemented, a highly efficient and prompt-free FSL framework that is based on the fine-tuning of a small sentence transformer model (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019) with an additional classifier head on top. SetFit has been shown to be competitive with fine-tuning a RoBERTa-large model on $\approx 3,000$ examples using only 8 labelled examples per class. The multilingual-e5-base sentence transformer (Wang et al., 2024), a 278M-parameter model, was fine-tuned due to its strong multilingual performance and computational efficiency. The model was optimised using a Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) (Watanabe, 2023), to maximise the F1 score on the validation set. The optimal hyperparameter values were $4.23e-5$ for the learning rate, 2 training epochs, batch size 16, and 10 iterations to generate sentence pairs.

The trained model was evaluated on the test set using accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. While the small dataset size introduces limitations in terms of generalisability, the results nonetheless provide a necessary indication of the model’s performance and are essential for assessing its practical utility. This semantic classifier was used in conjunction with the emotion and sentiment analysis outputs to further filter and analyse posts related to perceived security concerns.

3.3 Spatial aggregation and classification

To investigate the geographic distribution of perceived security concerns, the posts from Milan and New York City were aggregated using an H3 hexagonal grid (Uber, 2018) at resolution 9, which provides an average edge length of 200.79 metres. This resolution was selected to ensure comparability with the security perception datasets acquired from the previous works mentioned above. For each H3 cell, several metrics were computed, specifically the number of posts that (i) expressed negative sentiment, (ii) contained indicators of fear, and (iii) were classified as relevant by our semantic few-shot classifier.

3.4 Spatial analyses and model testing

To test the accuracy and the validity of the classification approaches described above, several strategies were implemented, devised in relation to the characteristics of the security perception data of the two case studies.

For the case of Milan, the comparison is against the security perception data acquired from the STEP UP project, which is a synthetic Safety Score which varies from 1 “*Feels very unsafe*” to 3 “*Feels very safe*”, the term “safe” referring here to a sense of security. In the context of the STEP UP project, the term “safety” was used in lieu of the term “security” to refer to women’s security perception. During the development of this metric, the threshold of 1.8 was identified as describing the area characterised by a feeling of uneasiness and danger. The same limit is maintained in this study for the sake of comparison. A first validation test consisted of the spatial coverage comparison between the relevant posts and the STEP UP data. Since the number of relevant posts is also influenced by a natural distribution of areas with varying levels of activity, a binary approach is adopted that classifies each hexagon cell by the presence or absence of relevant posts. The second validation test was to calculate the average value of the unfiltered Safety Score data, for the complete distribution and for the subset of hexagons with at least one relevant post.

For the case of New York City, the comparison is against the reported crimes and violations. In this case, the dataset is a set of points, which was intersected with the H3 grid, calculating the quantity of points per cell. Similarly to the Milan approach, the first test consisted in the spatial coverage comparison of the binary classification (i.e., *present or absent*). For that reason, the evaluation focused on the estimate of (i) the true positive cases (when the cell with a relevant post also has crime-related data points), (ii) the false positive cases (when the cell with a relevant post does not have any crime-related data point), (iii) the false negative cases (when the cell without a relevant post has crime-related data points), and (iv) true negative cases (when the cell without relevant posts does not have any crime-related data point). A second validation test consisted in calculating the Pearson Correlation within the two data distributions, considering the quantity of relevant posts and the amount of crime-related data points.

3.5 Social media-based keyword analysis

A final test was conducted on the collected X social media datasets and leveraged the keyword lookup strategy developed for the Google Places tests. This approach, while being less complex than the language analyses described above, was introduced to further test the relevance of social media data in the context of security perception. The utilisation of a contextually or potentially relevant keyword list (see *Table 4*) reduces the complexity to the mere presence or absence of significant terms in the analysed corpora. Moreover, a similar approach was tested in some of the authors previous work (Messa et al., 2021) and yielded interesting results in the evaluation of the occurrence of specific terms in different phases of the Covid-19 pandemic. Similarly to the tests conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the semantic classifiers, the evaluation method in this study consists of a binary classification (i.e., *mentioned, not mentioned*) of the selected word list, to be compared with a binary classification of the baseline security perception data: the STEP UP Safety Index for the case of Milan, and the crime distribution data for the case of New York City.

3.6 Google Place reviews validation and analysis

As mentioned in section 2.3, parallel to the analysis of X microblogging data, the study of Google Places data (Google Maps place reviews) was carried out as a supplementary analysis to explore an alternative geo-social media data source for security perception in Milan where social media data coverage was found to be low. To assess the relevance of these reviews to the topic of perceived security for women in public space, the SetFit model, previously trained and validated on social media data, was applied. This model was used to classify reviews based on their semantic alignment with the research theme.

To validate the performance of the model when applied to a different data source, a multi-step manual verification process was conducted: (i) a random subset of 350 reviews was manually reviewed to evaluate the general performance of the model across the dataset, (ii) a second subset of 401 reviews was selected based on the presence of at least one term from a non-

exhaustive list of contextually or potentially relevant keywords and their derivatives as listed in Table 44, (iii) a third subset of 204 reviews classified by the model as relevant with a confidence score above 0.7 were selected, providing insight into the reliability of high-confidence predictions.

Table 44 - Non-exhaustive list of contextually relevant keywords.

Keywords				
safe	security	calm	serene	protected
monitored	well-lit	patrolled	well-frequented	lively
well-kept	reliable	welcoming	hospitable	orderly
familiar	reassuring	clean	unsafe	fear
dangerous	unsettling	abandoned	dirty	dark
degraded	neglected	isolated	threatening	criminal
petty criminal	theft	aggressive	vandalism	drug dealing

The validation aimed to assess both the accuracy of the model's predictions and its applicability across different content types and place categories. An analysis was then conducted, comparing model predictions with manual annotations to identify patterns of agreement and error, with the aim to understand distribution of relevance by place type, examining whether certain categories (e.g., parks, public transport stations) were more likely to contain reviews related to perceived security concerns. This combined qualitative and quantitative validation provided insights into the transferability of the model and informed the interpretation of review relevance across the dataset.

4. Results

4.1 Dataset statistics

Table Table 55 shows the statistical properties of the retrieved X datasets for both Milan 2019 and NYC 2021 after the steps of data cleaning and filtering. As in the original retrieved dataset (see Table 1), the cleaned NYC dataset is substantially larger, comprising over 1.1 million unique posts from 104,826 users, compared to 142,054 posts from 25,985 unique users in Milan. The proportion of posts containing images or videos varies across datasets, with Milan at approximately 19% and NYC at approximately 16%. The retention rate, the share of posts kept in the cleaned dataset, also differs between the two case studies, with Milan at 14.5% and NYC at 9.6%.

Table 55 - Statistical properties of the retrieved datasets after data filtering and cleaning.

Dataset	Original geometry	Unique posts	Unique users	Images / videos	Retention rate
Milan 2019	Point	120,927	18,174	8,310	-
	Bounding box	21,127	8,772	18,839	-
	Total	142,054	25,985	27,149	14.5%
NYC 2021	Point	986,122	57,960	53,183	-
	Bounding box	163,536	50,251	130,305	-
	Total	1,149,658	104,826	183,488	9.6%

The relative distribution of post languages across the two retrieved datasets is depicted in Figure **Error! Reference source not found.**. In Milan, most posts were in Italian (51.0%), followed by English (29.3%) and Spanish (3.9%), with other languages collectively accounting for 15.8% of the posts. In contrast, the NYC dataset was overwhelmingly dominated by English-language posts (93.6%), with Spanish (2.3%) and other languages (4.0%) representing only a small portion of tweets. These differences reflect the expected language contexts of the two cities and highlight the predominance of English in NYC's online discourse, as well as the prevalence of English among X users in either city.

Figure 1 - Relative distribution of languages across the cleaned datasets.

4.2 Semantic classification performance

The classification performance of the semantic few-shot classifier on the small test dataset of 29 examples is depicted in Table 6. The overall accuracy of the model is 0.72, meaning that 21 out of 29 posts were correctly classified. For the not relevant class, the model achieved perfect precision (1.00), meaning that every post predicted as not relevant was correct. However, the recall for the class was only 0.62, indicating that the model missed several not relevant posts by incorrectly labelling them as relevant. For the relevant class, the model achieved perfect recall (1.00), correctly identifying all relevant posts in the test set. However, in this case, the precision was only 0.50, meaning that half of the posts predicted as relevant were not relevant. These results suggest that the classifier is generally capable of identifying relevant posts and likely produces many false positives. For this reason, the semantic classification model is used in combination with sentiment and emotion detection to better filter for posts that not only mention relevant topics, but also express meaningful concerns or perceived threat.

Table 66 - Accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score and support of our semantic few-shot classifier on the test data.

	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Support
Not relevant	1.00	0.62	0.76	21
Relevant	0.50	1.00	0.67	8
Accuracy			0.72	29

The low precision of the classifier became evident when applied to the full datasets. In Milan (2019), 84,290 posts (59.3%) were classified as relevant, and in New York City (2021), 795,144 posts (69.2%) were labelled as relevant. A qualitative inspection confirmed that many posts marked as relevant included generic statements, ambiguous context and off-topic content. For this reason, another classification was tested, evaluating the posts for a joint indicator that flags security-relevant posts only if they are simultaneously (i) semantically relevant, (ii) negative in sentiment, and (iii) expressing fear. This stricter filter dramatically reduced the number of identified posts, resulting in 711 posts (0.501%) for Milan and 3,773 posts (0.328%) for NYC meeting all three criteria. A manual review showed that this subset more realistically captured posts expressing actual concern, discomfort or perceived threat.

4.3 Spatial analyses and model tests

Figure 13 shows the spatial distribution of geo-referenced posts aggregated per H3 grid cell (resolution 9) for Milan in 2019 and New York City in 2021. In Milan, posting activity is strongly concentrated in the city centre, with a notable drop

in the number of posts toward the outskirts. Conversely, New York City shows a more dispersed distribution of activity, with dense clusters of posts in Manhattan, parts of Brooklyn and Queens, and along major transit corridors. The broader spatial spread in NYC reflects its larger population and a widespread usage of X.

Figure 2 – Number of posts aggregated on the H3 grid (resolution level 9), for Milan (left) and NYC (right). The legend is the same for comparability.

Additionally, the spatial distribution of posts that were simultaneously classified as semantically relevant, negative in sentiment and expressing fear is visualised in Figure 4. This combination acts as a proxy for posts that may reflect perceived security concerns. In both cities, the number of cells containing at least one post that meets all three criteria is more limited than the complete dataset. The NYC map shows a higher number of cells with such posts, more evenly distributed across the city, similarly to the distribution of the complete dataset, with Midtown and Downtown Manhattan almost completely covered. Overall, the spatial patterns suggest that security-related concerns on X are more geographically widespread in NYC than in Milan.

Figure 3 – Simultaneously relevant posts (for the three criteria) aggregated on H3 grid (resolution level 9), for Milan (left) and NYC (right). The legend is the same for comparability.

In general, the outcomes of the validation tests outlined to estimate the effectiveness of the approaches to anticipate perceived security do not show meaningful results. Specifically, both tests for Milan and both tests for NYC failed to show any consistency between the distribution of the security perception data and the social media data analysis results (see Table 7).

For the case of Milan, the first validation test showed that out of 1,114 hexagons with a Safety Index (*SI*) lower than 1.8, only 96 cells included at least one relevant post, which represents 8.6% of the cases. Similarly, the second test showed that the average *SI* value for the complete hexagon distribution is 1.810, while the average *SI* value for the hexagon subset that had at least 1 relevant post is 2.012. A higher value of the *SI* represents a safer condition. Thus, the areas identified with the binary classification of the model’s results do not capture areas with a lower sense of security.

For the case of New York City, the validation tests showed similar results, with the first test showing that there is no spatial coverage relationship between social media data and the crime-related data (see *Table 7*). While the true positives show good coverage, with 75.8% of the hexagons with a relevant post also having crime-related data, the false negatives are particularly significant, with 83.0% of the hexagons with crime-related data not captured by the presence of a relevant post. The second test showed a non-significant correlation between the two datasets, with an *r* value of 0.068.

Table 77 – Validation tests results for the Milan and NYC case studies.

	Validation test description	Validation test result
Milan	First validation test	
		1,114 Hexagons with <i>SI</i> < 1.8
	Spatial coverage comparison between hexagons with <i>SI</i> < 1.8 and hexagons with at least one relevant post.	1,108 Hexagons with <i>SI</i> < 1.8 & with no relevant posts
		96 Hexagons with <i>SI</i> < 1.8 & with relevant posts
	Second validation test	
	1.810 Mean <i>SI</i> value for the complete hexagon dataset	
	2.012 Mean <i>SI</i> value for the subset of hexagons with at least 1 relevant post per cell.	
NYC	First validation test	
		712 True positive: a cell with relevant post also has crime-related data
	Spatial coverage comparison between hexagons with crime-related data and hexagons with at least one relevant post.	227 False positive: a cell with relevant post does not have any crime-related data
		3,471 False negative: a cell without relevant post has crime-related data
		96 True negative: a cell without relevant post also does not have any crime-related data
	Second validation test	
	Pearson correlation between the quantity of relevant posts and the crime-related data points per each hexagon	0.068 Correlation coefficient

4.4 Social media-based keyword spatial coverage

The final test related to the acquired social media data consisted of the binary classification of presence in each post of a list of contextually or potentially relevant keywords (see *Table 4*), similarly to the approach implemented for the analysis of the Google Places data. The results of this test are shown in *Figure 5 as a bivariate map*, with the overlapping distribution shown for the case of Milan and the case of New York City. Given the hexagons showing only baseline security perception data are more widespread and present than those indicating security perception data and relevant keyword overlap, it is possible to draw similar conclusions to those outlined in previous tests (see *Table 7*). Specifically, the social media-based analysis fails to capture the complexity and the distribution of security-driven data, limiting its coverage to the areas with a higher presence of posts. This phenomenon is inferable by the comparison of *Figures 3 and 4* against *Figure 5*, where only the areas with a higher number of posts appear as relevant in the keyword analysis. The results from X, therefore, appear to be too dependent on the locations of the posts and the selection of keywords is not effective enough to capture the nuances of the phenomenon of security perception.

Figure 4 – Comparison between the spatial coverage of X-based keyword analysis and the baseline security perception data, for the case of Milan (left) and New York City (right).

4.5 Google Places data analysis

The validation process revealed that the SetFit model, originally trained on social media data, does not effectively generalise to Google Places data. The substantial differences in language structure, tone, and context between posts and user-generated reviews significantly reduce the model's ability to accurately identify content related to perceived security for women. These findings point to the necessity of developing a tailored model specifically adapted to the characteristics of Google Places review data.

Manual verification confirmed the model's limited performance, with a generally low presence of relevant content across the dataset. In the manual verification process discussed in section 3.6, only 8% of textual reviews were found to be directly related to the topic. This percentage increased slightly to 17% among the reviews classified by the model as relevant with high confidence (*i.e.*, confidence score above 0.7), and to 20% in the subset selected based on the presence of potentially relevant keywords. The model's performance improved significantly when the analysis was restricted to specific categories of places, particularly those related to transport, such as public transport stops and stations. Within this subset, 24% of randomly selected reviews were deemed relevant, while the keyword-based selection showed a much higher relevance rate of 57%. Even among high-confidence predictions for these transport-related places, 22% of reviews were identified as relevant. A similar pattern was observed in reviews associated with parks. In the keyword-based subset, the share of relevant reviews increased to 39%, suggesting that specific place types may be more likely to contain content touching on themes of safety and security.

Overall, these results suggest that while a general-purpose model trained on social media data does not translate well to Google reviews data, there is clear potential in developing place-type-specific models or applying a typology-sensitive approach to improve relevance detection in this new context. At the same time, the API-imposed cap on the number of retrievable reviews per location and free query limits the depth of content analysis using the proposed methods. As a result, the findings should be interpreted as indicative rather than exhaustive, underscoring the need for expanded access or alternative data sources in future work.

5. Conclusions and Future Works

5.1 Synthesis and Discussion

Our findings suggest that geo-social media data only marginally reflects localised expressions of perceived insecurity in the cases under study and lacks the consistency and spatial coverage required to serve as a robust indicator of urban security at city scale. In Milan, posting activity was highly centralised, with relevant posts appearing only sporadically in peripheral areas. In contrast, NYC exhibited a more spatially dispersed pattern, with clusters of security-related content emerging in the Bronx, Brooklyn, Queens, and Jersey City. These patterns align with population size and social media usage differences between the two cities. When the X-based analysis outcomes were compared to available security

perception data from the same time periods (Gorrini et al., 2021; Messa et al., 2025), all the proposed tests failed to show a reliable relation between the two phenomena. This suggests that, while social media data may highlight emerging issues or public discourse around security, it does not reflect broader population-level perceptions captured through traditional surveys, crowdsourced data or reported crime and violation data.

5.2 Research Limitations

Several limitations currently hinder the effective use of geo-social data for large-scale urban analyses across the European Union. First, the quality of geolocation in social media data, particularly for X data, remains a major challenge. Since 2019, most X posts are tagged with place-based bounding boxes rather than precise GPS coordinates (Khalid, 2019), leading to datasets much smaller than anticipated as bounding box geometries often cover entire neighborhoods or even entire cities and are incompatible with the required granularity. Moreover, X geotags can be manually selected and do not necessarily indicate the user's real-time location (Serere & Resch, 2025). Additionally, geo-tagged locations in posts could also refer to the location of the user while posting, which may differ from the location the subject of the post is about. Earlier versions of Twitter offered more precise GPS-tagged data, which historically enabled fine-grained urban analyses (Resch et al., 2016). However, this level of spatial resolution is no longer available at scale due to policy changes of social media platforms, including restricted API access and limited location sharing capabilities for users. These limitations underscore the need for more precise and reliable geospatial references in social media platforms. Currently, no platform provides both high-resolution geolocations and semantically rich textual content at scale.

Second, there is no widely accepted definition of what constitutes security-related content on social media. Our few-shot semantic classifier was trained on a small, manually labelled dataset, which limited its precision and generalisability. To address this, we introduced a joint indicator combining semantic relevance, negative sentiment, and expressions of fear. This reduced the proportion of posts identified as security-relevant to below 1% in both cities (0.501% in Milan; 0.328% in NYC), resulting in a more focused and realistic subset. However, the performance of this approach is constrained by the lack of large-scale annotated datasets. Multilingualism further complicates classification, as relevant expressions may differ across languages and cultures. We also explored alternative semantic methods, such as BERTopic (Grootendorst, 2022) including guided zero-shot variants, but all of them produced overly generic topics and failed to isolate security-related themes. Keyword filtering likewise proved insufficient due to a large overlap with unrelated content.

Thirdly, differences in social media usage patterns likely influenced the results. In 2019, the user penetration of X (then known as Twitter) in Italy was 19%, compared to 25% in the United States (Cornia, 2019; Jenkins & Graves, 2021). Additionally, NYC has a significantly larger population than Milan (8.4 million vs. 1.4 million), which helps explain the greater volume and spatial diversity of posts in NYC. Previous research has shown that social media activity varies with sociodemographic characteristics (Wood-Doughty et al., 2017), but there is limited evidence on how such factors affect posts related to perceived security. To date, no studies have systematically investigated security-related social media behaviour across different user groups or cultural contexts.

Our alternative keyword-based classification approach did not lead to significant changes in the representation of security-induced distributions, despite the manual and discretionary selection of contextually or potentially relevant keywords. The hexagons with relevant data follow a spatial distribution that is similar to the general coverage of unfiltered social media data, showing how security-related phenomena are not correctly captured by this approach, and, potentially, not significantly present in the content of the social media posts.

The research exploring Google Places reviews in Milan also highlighted several limitations related both to the data source and to the research design. One of the main constraints lies in the use of Google Places API, which limits access to reviews, providing a maximum of five reviews per place and imposing restrictions on the number of free queries. These limitations not only reduce the volume of accessible data but also pose cost-related barriers for large-scale analysis. As a result, our analysis was based on a relatively small and randomly selected subset of 1,009 places, which may not provide comprehensive coverage of the urban environment. This limited dataset could introduce biases in the findings,

particularly in the representation of specific types of places or user demographics. In addition, the SetFit model trained on social media data proved to be ineffective when applied to Google reviews, underscoring the need for models specifically fine-tuned to the linguistic and contextual characteristics of review texts. Nevertheless, the current results suggest that transport-related places, such as bus stops and train stations, and parks show higher potential for detecting relevant content on perceived security, indicating promising directions for future research.

5.3 Future Work

The need for a scalable and effective methodology to estimate the complex, socio-spatial phenomenon of perceived urban security is of the utmost importance, as it would enable planners and decision makers to take informed decisions about how city users interact with urban environments. Characterising the transport infrastructure by its perceived security could enable the inclusion of this factor when measuring accessibility to services and opportunities, as well as evaluating its impact on potential instances of transport poverty and the related risk of social exclusion. Within this framework, several factors appear as particularly relevant: *(i)* the granularity of the analysis level; *(ii)* the need to account for different demographics and socio-economic characteristics; *(iii)* the relation with site-specific factors and context; and *(iv)* the inclusion of temporal dynamics to understand fluctuations in security perception over time. While geo-social media data appears to be a potential source of information capable of meeting the required factors outlined above, several limitations emerged in this study, shedding light on the actual reliability and applicability of geo-social media content in characterising urban security perception for transport policy analysis.

Future research should address the authenticity and reliability of geosocial media and place-based data sources. Social media content is highly heterogeneous, comprising user-generated posts (e.g., text or images) as well as automated activity from bots or external services (e.g., website feeds or reposted content). Similarly, Google Place reviews may contain sponsored entries that do not reflect genuine user experiences. To ensure analytical validity, robust filtering strategies are required to only retain authentic, human-made contributions that are relevant to the topic under study. In transport-related studies, it is also important to ensure that geotagged information accurately reflects actual static locations in the city and is not indicative of a transit environment (i.e. experience within a moving vehicle), which is neither static nor necessarily representative of the surrounding urban context. In the case of place-based user reviews, it is also imperative to filter review content to focus specifically on experiences of public spaces rather than private or indoor environments. While such filtering is essential, it may considerably reduce the volume of usable content.

Moreover, advances in geolocation accuracy for social media data are needed, either through platform-level improvements or post-processing techniques that infer more precise locations from text, user metadata or patterns of behaviour. This is particularly relevant in relation to bounding boxes and geolocation linked to specific places rather than true coordinates. Place-specific data sources like Google Place reviews may be more promising than free-text social media posts in terms of locational accuracy, since these are directly associated with specific geolocations across the city. That said, larger place typologies such as parks, or airports, may decrease granularity of results, limiting interpretability of security perception data.

The quality of the analysed data is heavily dependent on the availability of relevant information in the original dataset, which is limited by the factors described above. Nevertheless, NLP techniques, such as the ones implemented in this study, are an effective tool to extract relevant information from the unstructured social media textual information. This research showed that the employed strategies were not completely successful in extracting relevant information from the original data, resulting in output with considerable false negatives and false positives. A larger, multilingual and more robustly annotated dataset is essential for training more robust classification models. Such a dataset should reflect varying expressions of security concerns across languages and demographics. Moreover, alternative lines of research should be tested, such as implementing LMM-based classification of social-media data, with a robust framework of accuracy tests to ensure the correctness in the captured meanings.

A promising direction for future research is the development of models that integrate multiple predictors, with geo-social media data as one component. Integrating geo-social data with complementary sources such as official crime statistics, environmental context, and survey-based perception data may help triangulate urban security insights and build more holistic, scalable frameworks for assessing perceived security of specific individual profiles in cities. Future research should therefore investigate user behaviour around transport security-related posting, including the demographic distribution of contributors, and contextual variances, including how coverage varies by city or country. However, this approach requires either ground truth data or alternative security-related data to calibrate such models, posing a conceptual limit to their replicability and scalability. While crowdsourced data offers a reliable source for model calibration, its availability is limited in scale and scope, as well as demographic representation. A multi-layered approach that integrates city-wide, local, and user-level factors from diverse data sources can provide a more nuanced understanding of perceived security.

Finally, while the STEP UP and New York study datasets on urban security provide valuable insights and strong referential points against which to compare geo-social media data, they are essentially “frozen in time.” Future research would benefit from systematically comparing this type of static, case-specific dataset with alternative or improved data sources for newly generated punctual data, including data processed from review-based platforms such as Google Places, to assess both consistency and temporal continuity in capturing security-related perceptions across a specific urban setting.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Credit authorship contribution statement

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